

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A study on faculty perspective towards alternative teaching practices (E-Learning — Blackboard) during COVID 19

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* **Corresponding author.**

jerlinmsnaccn@gmail.com

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Jerlin Priya Lovelin Auguskani^{1*}

¹ Assistant Professor, Faculty of Nursing, University College, Aldarb, Jazan University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Background/Objectives: The novel coronavirus causing COVID 19 has emerged at the end of 2019 as a threat to the health and wellbeing of millions of people within a few weeks of its outbreak. Globally, many institutions replace traditional teaching with online mode. A sudden transition of teaching has its merits and demerits. Keeping this in view, the present study is focused to assess the perception of the faculty Alternative teaching practices (E-Learning – Blackboard) concerning COVID 19. **Methods:** A semi-structured survey questionnaire was used for data collection. The analysis was based on 42 faculties who had been working in selected colleges at Jizan province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Descriptive statistics are used to analyze the data. **Findings:** The findings of the study related to the faculty perspective were grouped into four categories. In the first category of analyzing perception of faculties towards the E-learning platform, it was found that all the faculties were using university platforms for E-learning. Due to a lack of previous experience nearly half of them experienced technical difficulties. In the second category, the perception of faculties about E-learning course delivery. It was mentioned that the student’s response was found less in the online class. It was further noted that online teaching was least effective for laboratory-based and clinical based courses. The third category emphasized E-learning difficulties experienced by faculties. The fourth category was the faculties’ perception of effective teaching mode. Majority of them disagreed to the statement that “Classroom teaching could be completely replaced by online teaching mode”. **Novelty:** While E-learning is on its pace in the field of education in the present generation. It may be a supplement for regular classroom teaching rather than a complete replacement, particularly practical oriented subjects. **Keywords:** COVID 19; E-Learning; traditional teaching; alternative teaching practices

1 Introduction

Globally, the outbreak of COVID 19 makes drastic changes in society. The Government of many countries has taken numerous initiatives to normalize the situation to promote the health and well being of society. The Higher Educational Institutions maintain the continuity of Educational activity through E-learning platforms. However, it needs much collaborative efforts among faculty, administrative staff, and students for successful completion. Though Online teaching is one of the innovations in the teaching and learning process, complete switch over from traditional teaching practices affects the students and teacher as well. There are many differences between Traditional teaching and online teaching methods. There are similar studies carried out in earlier days to assess the educational policies and practices. Presently, the researcher would like to find the difference of opinion among the teaching fraternity regarding Online teaching mode to overcome the shortcomings in the future. The purpose of the study was to assess the faculty’s perception of Alternative teaching practices (E-Learning – Blackboard) during COVID 19.

1.1 Teaching and learning approaches with technology

The concept of teaching includes teacher-focused and learner-focused methods. In the teacher-focused method, knowledge is transmitted by the teacher to learners with the use of technology. In such a case, the teacher needs to have a better orientation towards the use of technology for effective teaching. In learner-focused teaching, the teacher instills knowledge in the learner actively using technology to achieve learning goals.

The learning pyramid, which was developed by the National Training Laboratories Institute, Bethel, Maine in the early 1960s proposes that the average retention rate is more in participatory method than in passive methods including lecturing, demonstrations used in classroom teaching. Also, discussions, practice by doing methods have a high retention rate but in an E-learning platform, it is highly unusual to adopt all participatory methods of teaching and learning.

Fig 1. Teaching & learning approaches with technology

1.2 Background of study

Chrysi Rapanta published an article on Online University Teaching during and after COVID 19 crisis, refocusing teacher presence and learning activity⁽¹⁾. Irini presented the global perspective on transforming ophthalmic education into virtual learning during COVID 19 pandemic⁽²⁾. Mohammed Amin Almaiah explored about the critical challenges and factors influencing the E-learning system usage during COVID 19 pandemic⁽³⁾. Ayman Elsamanoundy published an article on enhancing students' engagement in using blackboard as an online learning community tool in clinical Biochemistry⁽⁴⁾. Wahab Ali presented Online and remote learning in Higher Education Institutes, a necessity in light of COVID 19 pandemic⁽⁵⁾. Alsadoon, E. published an article on the impact of an adaptive e-course on students' achievements based on the students' prior knowledge, Education and Information Technologies⁽⁶⁾. Eman Walabe submitted a Postdoctoral thesis to the University of Ottawa regarding E-Learning Delivery in Saudi Arabian Universities⁽⁷⁾. Wei Bao studied COVID 19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking University. The study concludes with five high impact principles for online education⁽⁸⁾. Amit Kumar Arora mentioned in his article that those who have adopted virtual mode, the mean of actual benefits is significantly less than the mean of expected benefits⁽⁹⁾. Abdullah Aljaber conducted a study titled on E-Learning policy in Saudi Arabia: Challenges and successes, Research in Comparative and International Education⁽¹⁰⁾. R. Raja et al. in 2018 published an article titled Impact of modern technology in education. Emphasized that technology is a gift of God. Technology has certainly changed the way we live. Further, stated that technology eases the task of teachers in the learning process⁽¹¹⁾. Paul et al. in the study of "The myths of the digital native and the multitasker" pointed out the present-day students belong to digital media world and fundamentally different from previous generations of students. They have been labeled as digital natives and can multitask⁽¹²⁾. Christine Frazer et al studied-on Faculty Perception of Online Teaching Effectiveness and Indicators of Quality in 2017. They mentioned that effective online teachers facilitate, connect, lead, and work in synchrony with students to obtain indicators of quality in teaching and learning⁽¹³⁾. Theresa Capra quoted in her article that online education has experienced dramatic expansion and growth. Although this growth is impressive, it doesn't occur without consequences. It was evident that there are many withdrawals and failures in online courses⁽¹⁴⁾. Heather et al highlighted that online learning is increasing these days, hence the teachers need to have good learning experiences to enable them equip the students with high-quality education thereby overcome the challenges faced by the online teaching process⁽¹⁵⁾.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants

The data has been collected from respective faculties of various discipline in which 7 (16.67%) from Nursing branch, 11 (26.9%) from Science department, 5 (11.9%) faculty from Math's discipline, 15 (33.3%) belongs to language studies and 4(9.52%) from the business department. In terms of teaching position of participants, there was 1(2.38%) professor, 2(4.76%) Associate professors, 13(30.95%) Assistant professors, 24(57.14%) lecturers, and 2(4.76%) others shared their views. Also, it was evident that the majority of 35 (83.33%) teaching faculties are experienced with more than 5 years and the least have in vice versa.

2.2 Instruments

To evaluate the faculty's perception of alternative teaching practices, a semi-structured survey questionnaire was used. It was originally constructed by the researcher, validated and revised by the consultant. The components of the survey consist of 2 sections with an overall 40 questions. The first section that comprised 6 questions was used to collect baseline information and the second section was the faculty perspective survey questionnaire which has four categories (E-learning platform, E-learning course delivery, E-learning difficulties, and Effective teaching mode) with a total of 34 questions.

2.3 Procedure

The survey was conducted through a self-administered questionnaire among the faculties online during the first two weeks of June 2020. The purpose of the study was mentioned in the questionnaire. The researcher emphasized the participants on voluntary participation and withdrawal. The participants are instructed about the data confidentiality procedure. Anonymity was also maintained. Institution permission was taken before the conduction of the study. Faculties who volunteered to participate filled out the questionnaire and the data collected through Email. The collected data was then analyzed using descriptive statistics at the end of June 2020.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Result on faculties' perception towards E-learning platform

Table 1. Frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception towards E-learning platform

S.No	E-learning platform	Variable	f	%
1.	The platform used for E-learning	University platform	42	100
		Zoom	-	-
		LMS/Moodle	2	4.76
		Microsoft teams	3	7.14
		University platform, LMS, Microsoft team	2	4.76
2.	Network mode used for E-learning	Wi-Fi	26	61.9
		Mobile data	8	19.05
		Wi-Fi & Mobile data	8	19.05
3.	Do you have previous experience in Online teaching mode?	Yes	9	21.43
		No	31	73.81
		Not sure	2	4.76
4.	Do you have experienced technical difficulty during the class	Yes	19	45.24
		No	21	50
		Not sure	2	4.76
5.	If yes, What is the difficulty?	Network Issue	10	23.81
		Hardware Issue	1	2.38
		Lack of awareness	1	2.38
		Network, Hardware issue, lack of awareness	2	4.76
		Network, hardware issue	2	4.76
		Network issue, lack of awareness	3	7.14
6.	What is the mode of conducting the class	Mobile phone	3	7.14
		Laptop	39	92.86
		Desktop	0	0
		Tablet	0	0
		Mobile & Laptop	3	7.14
7.	What is the average number of classes delivering in a day	1-2	8	19.05
		2-4	30	71.43
		4-6	4	9.52
8.	What is the online class strength in terms of traditional classroom teaching?	Less	27	64.29
		More	8	19.05
		No difference	7	16.7
9.	What is the average number of extra hours you spend on the computer for classwork in a day?	1-2 hours	5	11.9
		2-4 hours	15	35.71
		more than 4 hours	22	52.38
10.	Do you spend extra time in the online teaching mode than traditional classroom teaching mode?	Yes	32	76.19
		No	8	19.05
		Not sure	2	4.76
11.	If Yes, specify the reason for spending extra time?	Class preparation	3	7.14
		Voice recording	1	2.38
		uploading files	0	0
		Assignment/test	3	7.14
		Attendance	0	0
		Class preparation, Voice recording, uploading files, Assignment, test, Attendance	17	40.48
		class preparation, Voice recording, Assignment, test, Attendance	2	4.76
		Class preparation, uploading files, Assignment/test, Attendance	2	4.76
		Voice recording, uploading files, Assignment/test, Attendance	2	4.76

Continued on next page

Table 1 continued

Class preparation, Voice recording, Assignment/Test	1	2.38
Class preparation, Assignment, Attendance	1	2.38
uploading files, Assignment, Attendance	1	2.38
Class preparation, voice recording	1	2.38
No response	8	19.05

Table 1 infers the frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception of the E-learning platform. According to the study findings, all the faculties 42 (100%) were using university platforms for E-learning. Along with university platforms, some were using synchronous and asynchronous methods. Regarding the network mode used by them, 26 (61.9%) were using Wi-Fi, 8 (19.05%) with mobile data and 8 (19.05%) were using both Wi-Fi and mobile data. 31 (73.81%) did not have previous experience in Online teaching mode. 21 (50%) did not experience technical difficulty during the class and nearly half of the 19 (45.24%) experienced so. Among the difficulties experienced, 10 (23.81%) mentioned network issues, at least around 2(4.76%) mentioned hardware issues and lack of awareness. Also, the majority of 39 (92.86%) were using laptops as the mode of conducting the class. Regarding the average number of classes delivered in a day, a maximum of 30 (71.43%) were delivered 2-4 hours. The majority of 27 (64.29%) faculties mentioned that the online class strength is less in terms of traditional classroom teaching. It is also found that 22 (52.38%) were spending more than 4 extra hours on the computer for classwork in a day and an average of 15 (35.71%) of around 2-4 hours. Accordingly, 32 (76.19%) stated that they spend extra time on online teaching mode than traditional classroom teaching mode. 17 (40.48%) were spending extra timings for class preparation, voice recording, uploading files, assignment, test, attendance.

3.2 Result on faculties' perception towards E-learning course delivery

Table 2. Frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception towards E-learning course delivery

S. No	E-learning course delivery	Variable	f	%
1.	What are the course contents used for course delivery?	Sharing Video/notes at the time of the lecture	14	33.33
		Sharing Video/notes before the lecture	9	21.43
		Spot lectures	4	9.52
		Sharing videos at the time and before a lecture, spot lectures	4	9.52
		Sharing videos at the time and before a lecture	5	11.9
		Sharing videos at the time and spot lectures	3	7.14
		Sharing videos before lecture and spot lectures	3	7.14
2.	Which of the below-mentioned methods is effective in use?	Sharing Video/notes at the time of the lecture	15	35.71
		Sharing Video/notes before the lecture	12	28.57
		Spot lectures	5	11.9
		Sharing videos at the time and before the lecture, spot lectures	2	4.76
		Sharing videos at the time and before the lecture	5	11.9
		Sharing videos at the time and spot lecture	3	7.14
3.	Did you record your lecture?	Yes	39	92.86
		No	3	7.14
4.	If yes, Are you comfortable in recording lectures?	Yes	26	61.9
		No	13	30.95
5.	If No, Specify the reason	Disconnection Issues	3	7.14
		Lack of voice clarity	1	2.38
		Disturbance in network	3	7.14
		Problems in uploading recorded clippings	0	0
		Disconnection issues, lack of voice clarity, disturbance in network & problems in uploading.	3	7.14

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Table 2 continued

		Disconnection issues, lack of voice clarity, disturbance in network.	2	4.76
		Disconnection issues, disturbance in the network & problems in uploading.	1	2.38
6.	How far is the student's response in the online class rather than classroom teaching?	Less	22	52.38
		Same	11	26.19
		More	4	9.52
		Not sure	5	11.9
7.	How far is the discipline of the online class rather than classroom teaching?	Less	21	50
		Same	9	21.43
		More	6	14.29
		No idea	6	14.29
8.	What is your response to the statement that the discipline of the class is affected in the Online learning process?	Strongly agree	6	14.29
		Agree	20	47.62
		Neutral	12	28.57
		Disagree	1	2.38
		Strongly disagree	1	2.38
		No response	2	4.76
		Not suitable	23	54.76
Neutral	18	42.86		
9.	Do you feel the quality of teaching and learning improved in On-line teaching?	Yes	11	26.19
		No	29	69.05
		Not sure	2	4.76
10.	If no, Specify the reason	Lack of classroom culture	5	11.9
		Difficulties in grading	4	9.52
		Difficulties in attendance	9	21.43
		Lack of classroom culture, difficulties in grading & attendance	8	19.05
		Lack of classroom culture & difficulties in grading	1	2.38
		Lack of classroom culture & difficulties in attendance	1	2.38
		Difficulties in grading & attendance	1	2.38
11.	What is the online assessment process adopted?	Quiz	9	21.43
		Assignment	3	7.14
		Discussion	1	2.38
		Quiz, assignment, discussion & oral examination	13	30.95
		Quiz, assignment, discussion & Homework	1	2.38
		Quiz, assignment & Homework	1	2.38
		Quiz, assignment, discussion	10	23.81
		Quiz, assignment & Homework	2	4.76
Quiz & assignment	2	4.76		

Table 2 a - enumerates the frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception towards E-learning course delivery. Accordingly, 14 (33.33%) used shared video/notes at the time of the lecture. 9 (21.43%) shared video/notes before the lecture, 4 (9.52%) performed spot lectures, and around 4 (9.52%) performed in a mixed way, respectively. Further 15 (35.71%) mentioned sharing video/notes at the time of lecture is more effective, also a similar number of faculties noted that sharing video/notes before the lecture was effective, few of 5 (11.9%) stated that spot lectures were effective. It was further clear that the majority of 39 (92.86%) recorded the lecture before the class. Among them, 26 (61.9%) were comfortable in recording the lecture and the remaining 13 (30.95%) on the other way round. Regarding difficulties in recording lectures, they stated the reason as

disconnection issues, disturbance in-network, lack of voice clarity, and problems in uploading. 22 (52.38%) faculties stated that the student’s response is less in the online class rather than classroom teaching, 11 (26.19%) mentioned that it’s similar, and very few faculties were towards the statement that the response rate is more. Also, 21 (50%) noted that the discipline is less towards online class rather than classroom teaching. With that, 26 (61.9%) agree with the statement that the discipline of the class is affected by the Online learning process. In addition to that 29 (69.05%) stated that the quality of teaching and learning is not improved in On-line teaching. The faculties stated the reason as there was a lack of classroom culture, difficulties in grading & maintaining attendance. The online assessment methods adopted by the faculties include Quiz, assignment, discussion, oral examination, Homework, and presentation.

3.3 Result on faculties’ perception towards E-learning course delivery

Fig 2. Effectiveness of online teaching about courses with a different methodology

Figure 2 illustrates the effectiveness of online teaching about courses with different methodologies. It was evident that online teaching was suitable for Theory-based courses and then to numerically based courses whereas not suitable for laboratory-based and clinical based courses.

3.4 Result on faculties’ perception towards E-learning difficulties

Table 3. Frequency & percentage distribution of faculties’ perception towards E-learning difficulties

S. No	E-learning difficulties	Variable	f	%
1.	Did you face any difficulties in the On-line assessment Process?	Yes	25	59.52
		No	14	33.33
		Not sure	3	7.14
2.	If Yes, mention the reason below	Difficult to monitor	3	7.14
		Performance assessment is more challenging	3	7.14

Continued on next page

Table 3 continued

		The student expects more visually rich and interacting materials	6	14.29
		Time-consuming	4	9.52
		Difficult to monitor, performance assessment is more challenging, students expect interacting materials & time consuming	3	7.14
		Difficult to monitor, performance assessment is more challenging & students expects interacting materials	1	2.38
		Difficult to monitor, performance assessment is more challenging, & time-consuming	3	7.14
		Performance assessment is more challenging, students expect interacting materials & time consuming	1	2.38
		Difficult to monitor & performance assessment is more challenging	1	2.38
3.	Did you face any difficulties in maintaining the attendance of the students?	Yes	22	52.38
		No	18	42.86
		Not sure	2	4.76
4.	If yes, specify the reason below	Inability to identify the proper reason for not attending the session	12	28.57
		Network Issues	10	23.81
5.	Did you experience any physical or emotional disturbance in Online teaching?	Yes	19	45.24
		No	21	50
		Not sure	2	4.76
		Eyestrain	1	2.38
		Back pain	1	2.38
		Sleep disturbances	0	0
		Headache	1	2.38
6.	If Yes, specify the reason below	Eye strain, back pain, sleep disturbance & Headache	7	16.67
		Eye strain, back pain, sleep disturbance	1	2.38
		Eye strain, back pain & Headache	2	4.76
		Back pain, sleep disturbance & Headache	1	2.38
		Eye strain & back pain	1	2.38
		Eye strain & Headache	3	7.14
		Back pain & Headache	1	2.38

Table 3 states the frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception towards E-learning difficulties. 25 (59.52%) mentioned that they have faced difficulties in the On-line assessment Process. They have difficulties including difficult to monitor, performance assessment is more challenging, and students expect interacting materials and time-consuming. 22 (52.88%) stated difficulties in maintaining the attendance of the students. The reason they mentioned includes the inability to identify the proper reason for not attending the session and network issues. Regarding physical or emotional disturbance in online teaching, 21 (50%) do not have any disturbance and remaining vice versa. The physical and emotional disturbance includes Eye strain, back pain, sleep disturbance & Headache.

3.5 Result on faculties' perception towards effective teaching mode

The majority of 26 (61.9%) disagreed with the statement "Classroom teaching be completely replaced by Online teaching mode" According to the study findings, faculties viewed traditional classroom teaching practices as effective in improving academic performance and the preferred mode of teaching. Further, it states that it is least important for laboratory and practical oriented subjects. The study also emphasized that it is not effective to maintain classroom culture and attendance in comparison to

traditional teaching practices.

Table 4. Frequency & percentage distribution of faculties' perception towards effective teaching mode

S. No	Effective teaching mode	Variable	f	%
1.	What is your response to the statement "Classroom teaching be completely replaced by Online teaching mode"	Strongly agree	1	2.38
		Agree	7	16.67
		Neutral	6	14.29
		Disagree	13	30.95
		Strongly disagree	13	30.95
		Not sure	2	4.96
2.	Which is your preferred mode of teaching?	Online Teaching	4	9.52
		Traditional classroom teaching	36	85.71
		Not sure	2	4.76

3.6 Discussion

The present study focused on the faculty perception of Alternative teaching practices (E-Learning – Blackboard) during COVID 19. The findings of the study were grouped into four categories comprising the E-learning platform, E-learning course delivery, E-learning difficulties, and Effective teaching mode. When analyzing, faculties' perception towards the E-learning platform, all the faculties were using university platforms for E-learning. In addition to that, they were using synchronous and asynchronous methods according to the availability of resources and study objectives. Wi-Fi was used as a network mode by many of them. Also, it was mentioned that many of the faculties do not have previous experience. Nearly half of them experienced technical difficulties including network issues, hardware issues, and lack of awareness. Many of them used laptops as the mode of conducting the class. It was also evident that an average of 2 to 4 hours of classes has been delivered in a day with additional spending of 4 hours for class preparation, voice recording, uploading files, assignment, test, attendance than the traditional classroom teaching. The Study conducted by Irini mentioned that the COVID-19 pandemic enacted great challenges in the field of Ophthalmology Education as well. The experience gained through virtual training platform, may change the traditional teaching practices in the world and provide new educational opportunities for both teachers and learners⁽²⁾. Also, Elsamanoudy has written in his article about the perception and satisfaction of second-year medical students concerning the Blackboard online platform. The student found it effective along with face to face classroom-based learning methods for better learning achievement⁽⁴⁾.

Another category is the faculties' perception of E-learning course delivery. Accordingly, many faculties used shared video/notes at the time of the lecture, some before the lecture, and few more performed spots lectures. They further mentioned sharing video/notes at the time of the lecture is more effective, than in other ways. It showed further evidence that most of them recorded the lecture and upload it before the online class. Also, many of them were comfortable in recording the lecture. Though there are some difficulties in recording lectures including disconnection issues, disturbance in-network, lack of voice clarity, and problems in uploading. The student's response was found less in the online class rather than in classroom teaching. Many of them noted that the discipline is less towards online class rather than classroom teaching. The quality of teaching and learning is not improved in On-line teaching. The faculties stated the reason as there was a lack of classrooms culture, difficulties in grading & maintaining attendance. The online assessment methods adopted by the faculties include Quiz, assignment, discussion, oral examination, Homework, and presentation. It was further evident that online teaching was suitable for Theory-based courses and then to numerically based courses whereas least effective for laboratory-based and clinical based courses. On contrary, Irini et al stated in the article that online learning becomes a useful platform to provide education of adult learners in terms of its cost, effectiveness, accessibility, and flexibility of time of place in delivering the course⁽²⁾.

The third category emphasized E-learning difficulties experienced by faculties. Those include difficulties in the On-line assessment Process. Also, monitoring performance assessment is more challenging, students' expectations of interacting materials, time consumption, maintenance of attendance become additional difficulties. There was a greater physical or emotional disturbance in online teaching than classroom teaching. Almaiah et al. explored the critical challenges and factors influencing the E-learning system usage during the COVID-19 pandemic in Education and information technologies. They enlisted technological challenges, individual challenges, cultural challenges, and course challenges. It may be a major suggestion for the policymakers, designers, developers, and researchers which enable them to get acquainted with the key aspects of E-

learning for successful usage during the COVID 19 pandemic⁽³⁾. Another study by Chrysi Sapanta states that online teaching and learning becomes a particular challenge and has been an urgent and unexpected request than face to face teaching. It implies certain pedagogical content knowledge especially to technological designing, organizing, and delivering course material for a better learning environment⁽¹⁾.

The fourth category was the faculties' perception of effective teaching mode. The majority of them disagreed with the statement "Classroom teaching be completely replaced by online teaching mode" According to the study findings, faculties mentioned that traditional classroom teaching practices as effective in improving academic performance and preferred mode of teaching. However, some researchers proved the effectiveness of online teaching in terms of students' achievement. Elham Alsadoon mentioned in the article that the impact of an adaptive e-course on students' achievement is not correlated with prior knowledge⁽⁶⁾.

In the field of education, the latest approaches have been in use including the application of technology, the use of modern aids, strategies in teaching, construction of need-based curriculum, independent evaluation strategies for the attainment of diversified competencies for past decades. Technology can only be used as a supplement. If online teaching continues, it will alter the educational landscape and new issues emerge among instructors and students. Preparation for teaching online is time-consuming and it extracts an additional 10 hours which eventually becomes a teaching load. Similarly, students have to face many struggles due to lack of social interaction, low grades than traditional classroom teaching which may result in sudden withdrawal from learning. To combat the limitations, it is necessary to follow certain principles including improvement in student-faculty contact, an adaptation of the active learning process, giving prompt feedback, and effective communication among teachers and students.

4 Conclusion

This study examined the faculties' view of alternative teaching practices during COVID 19. According to the result, it was evident that they are comfortable with regular classroom teaching rather than E-learning practices. Though the current students were born in the age of digital media with high potential in learning multiple intelligence approaches, sudden transformation doesn't occur without consequences. The teachers are facing many challenges due to the sudden transition of new technology. Difficulties in alternative teaching practices, course delivery, assessment process, and teaching mode were the major concern for the faculties. In addition to that, a lack of social interaction seems to be a concern for the teaching-learning process. While E-learning is on its pace in the field of education in the present generation. It can only be a supplement for regular classroom teaching rather than a complete replacement, particularly practical oriented subjects.

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